

NATIONAL DEVELOPMENT STRATEGIES OF NIGERIA BETWEEN 1972 AND 1985

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ABSTRACT

Nigeria has gone through a series of national economic crises over the years which have caused serious challenges to national development. This has positioned the country in a search for an adequate development strategy toward attaining national development in recent times. This has created the need to assess previous national development strategies to draw out an understanding of what we as a nation have done before, how it works and what we should expect from such development strategies. This research paper examines the national development strategies of Nigeria between 1972 and 1985. It considered the development strategies of different administrations and analysis shows that developmental strategies in Nigeria are; the First National Development Plan (1962-1968), the Second National Development Plan (1970-1974), the Third National Development Plan (1975-1980), the Fourth National Development Plan (1981-85), and the Post Fourth Plan Period (1985 to 1990). In Nigeria, several attempts were made to effect both rural and national development from independence apart from the various rolling plans, including the Agricultural Development Project (ADP), Green Revolution, Operation Feed the Nation, and others.

KEYWORDS: National Development Strategies, Development Plans, Development Programmes and Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

The Nigerian government has aspired to achieve development through various types of plans, namely short-term (Annual Budget), medium and long-term plans (Marcellus, 2009). Most development strategies ever adopted for use in Nigeria have been the same, with slight differences in their objectives, they are just mere nomenclature, and that is why the problem of development has persisted. We are often faced with a myriad of questions as to why Nigeria has remained on a point, nations that came into the international scene a few years back have been able to seek themselves out by overcoming the challenge of underdevelopment, and despite the huge endowment in Nigeria (natural and human) the

country situation remain unabated, there were nations colonized and has been able to get there footings, and also nations that jettison both the modernization and the dependency argument and these have place Nigeria in a position that is asking for what else then is to be done and what is the way forward for the development of this nation. The paradigm for development favouring development in the Western world has had a dereliction on the developing nations with specific attention on Nigeria; the top-down development paradigm will be compared with the down-up development paradigm. The top-down development strategies in Africa in general and Nigerians in particular have generally not raised the living standards among the rural poor. It is argued that appropriate development strategies have stemmed from methodologies that fail to appreciate the whole picture in rural communities and ignore local people's perceptions, needs and understanding (Olawepo, 2004).

DEVELOPMENT STRATEGIES IN NIGERIA

The following are the various development strategies that have been adopted at one time or the other. These are: community boards of 1954, the Farm Settlement Scheme of 1959, The First National Development Plan Period (1962-68); The Second National Development Plan Period (1974-1980); The Third National Development Plan Period (1975-80); The Fourth National Development Plan Period (1980-85); and the Post Fourth Plan Period (1985 to 1990), the Agricultural Development Project, Operation Feed the Nation, National Directorate for Employment, Green Revolution, Mass Mobilization for Self-reliance and Economic Recovery, River Basin Development Authority, National Accelerated Food Production Programme, the National Livestock Development Programme, the Directorate of Food, Roads and Rural Infrastructures, the Integrated Rural Development Programmes, the National Economic Empowerment and Development Strategy, the Vision 2010, the Vision 2020, the Seven Point Agenda and the likes (Ohagwu, 2010; Ezeah, 2005; Ndukwe, 2005; Igbokwe and Enwere, 2001)

Brief overviews of a few developmental strategies in Nigeria are:

The First National Development Plan (1962-1968)

The plan made no clear statement on rural infrastructural development, as agriculture was still an important exchange earner; the plan's objectives were to encourage the assemblage of agricultural produce for export purposes.

The Second National Development Plan (1970-1974)

The Second plan was launched shortly after the end of the civil war. The plan

attempted to rehabilitate economic activities in the war-affected areas. The plan spelt out five principal national objectives meant to achieve a united, just, strong and self-reliant nation. But just as in the first plan; the government did not make any clear statement on rural infrastructural development. However, it was stated in the plan that the government was committed to village regrouping. This was perhaps to reduce the cost of providing economic and social infrastructure such as health, electricity, water and educational facilities for the rural areas.

The Third National Development Plan (1975-1980)

Serious concern for rural development at the national level was first highlighted in the third national radical package towards the rural infrastructural development plan. The objectives of the plan are similar to those of the second national development plan. The plan emphasized the need to reduce regional disparities to foster national unity through the adoption of integrated rural development. The plan provided for a rural electrification scheme, and the establishment of River Basin Development Authorities (RBDAs). The construction of small dams and boreholes for rural water supply the clearing of feeder roads for the evacuation of agricultural produce and the supply of electricity to rural areas from large irrigation Dams. At the State Level, some governments, like Oyo State, showed their intention to transform the rural areas through the provision of basic infrastructural facilities.

The Fourth National Development Plan (1981-85)

The Fourth National Development Plan exhibits several distinguishing features. First, it was formulated by a civilian government under a new constitution based on the presidential system of government. Second, it was the first plan in which the local government tier was allowed to participate fully in its own right. The plan emphasized among other things the need for balanced development of the different sectors of the economy and of the various geographic areas of the country. It emphasized the importance of rural infrastructural development as a vehicle for enhancing the quality of rural life. In terms of rural transportation development, the local government in the country planned for the provision of intercity/village bus services, the construction of motor parks, and petrol filling stations during the fourth plan period (1981-85).

To increase the access of rural dwellers to safe drinking water, rural water supply schemes were planned apart from the huge borehole drilling programme. At the state level, the various state governments spelt out different policy issues in the fourth development plan. For instance, in Oyo State, the government identified four cardinal programs for itself. These include;

- (a) Free education at all levels
- (b) Free medical services
- (c) Integrated rural development and
- (d) Gainful employment

The Post-Fourth Plan Period (1985 to 1990):

The post-fourth plan period witnessed the establishment of the Directorate for Food, Roads and Rural Infrastructure (DFRRI) in 1985 to provide rural infrastructure in the countryside. The laws establishing the Directorate were promulgated under Decree Number Four of 1987. The core of the Directorate's Programme is the promotion of productive activities. Besides, the Directorate recognized the provision of rural infrastructure such as feeder roads, water, electricity and housing as essential for the enhancement of the quality of life in the rural areas.

The Programme of the Directorate includes:

- The organization and mobilization of the local people to enhance or facilitate closer interaction between the government and the people. In addition, the local communities were asked to form unions or associations to provide common facilities for themselves;
- The provision of rural infrastructures such as rural feeder roads, rural water and sanitation, rural housing and electrification;
- The promotion of productive activities such as food and agriculture, rural industrialization and technology;
- The promotion of other extracurricular activities such as socio-cultural and recreational programs, and intra and inter-community cohesion activities.

The plan for the implementation of DFRRI programs was organized into two phases, the target was to provide water for 250 communities in each of the states of the federation, to construct 90,000km of feeder roads, and to promote rural housing, health and agriculture. To facilitate industrial growth, and improve the attractiveness of the rural environment, the Directorate planned to commence its rural electrification Programme in the second phase starting in June 1987. In pursuit of its objectives, DFRRI also planned to cooperate with the organization (Ikotun, 2010)

In Nigeria several attempts were made to effect both rural and national development from independence apart from the various rolling plans, they include the agricultural development project (ADP), green Revolution, Operation Feed the Nation, and others. The various aforementioned strategies for development have all been the same, it is just a change of nomenclature, their objectives and medium for achieving the various goals have not been

different from one another.

The Agricultural Development Project (ADP)

This initiative was on the advice of the World Bank in 1970, the pilot projects were started in Funtua, Gombe, and Gasua, and the Programme was also expanded to other states such as Plateau State (the Lafia Agricultural Development Project now in Nasarawa State), Kogi, Benue, Kwara and Oyo State. The objective is to improve the living conditions of the low-income earners resident in rural areas, this implies the supply of farm inputs like fertilizers, fungicides, pesticides, and high-yielding variety seeds, credit facilities in cash and kind, land clearing services, the development of feeder roads and extension services. This brought about significant growth recorded in the agricultural sector in the late 1980s to early 1990s but the main challenge was the withdrawal of funds by the World Bank (Ogundele, 2008; Ohagwu, 2010).

Operation Feed the Nation

Operation Feed the Nation was introduced just as the time the National Accelerated Food Projection Programme (NAFPP) was introduced by the Federal Military Government in 1976, to create awareness about the importance of agriculture in National development. The Programme was designed to involve all the segments who were engaged during the long vacation, it was for a cross breeding of ideas from school and traditional knowledge. The Programme faced out at the expiration of the regime that introduced it. The problem with the Programme was that its birth was spontaneous without specific and measurable objectives (Ndukwe, 2005; Ohagwu, 2010)

In the recent past, the following were the development Programme in the wake of the return to democratic government, the National Economic Empowerment and Development Strategy (NEEDS), and the seven-point agenda. The President of Botswana Mr Festus Mogae, during his presentation, had a wise thought for our policymakers, according to him, "Nigeria could grow its economy through focused, honest leadership, with well-defined and coordinated national priorities"(Peterside, 2003).

CONCLUSION

The various strategies adopted by the Nigerian governments had been just a change in the nomenclature, the formulations and the process of implementation are the same, it is believed that we cannot continue doing the same thing repeatedly and expect different results

therefore, for development to thrive in Nigeria, the attitude and orientation of the implementers of the various strategies must change. Commitment and honesty on the part of the policymakers and implementers remain the only antidote to developmental challenges and the ineffectiveness of the strategies for development.

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